

Exploring the Translation Strategies of Taboos in Subtitled English Crime Movies into Persian: An In-depth Analysis

Aynaz Samir

English Department, Tabaran Institute of Higher Education, Mashhad, Iran.

E-mail: aynazsamir20@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: The translation of taboo words presents a significant challenge for translators in the audiovisual industry. The appropriate handling of the translation of taboo words is imperative, as their usage has the potential to transgress the cultural norms of the recipient society. In this context, translators employ diverse strategies to identify corresponding expressions in the target language. This study tried to identify the various types of taboo words based on Hughes' (1998) model in four crime movies namely Training Day (2001), 21 Jump Street (2012), Alpha Dog (2007), and Straight Outta Compton (2015). Furthermore, this study aimed to explore the strategies used by Iranian translators in subtitling the taboo words in the selected mentioned movies based on Davoodi's (2009) model. Descriptive statistics were used to determine frequencies and percentages of the found taboo words and applied strategies in the Persian subtitled of the taboo words. Based on Hughes' (1998) model, five different categories of taboo words including anatomy terms, excretion terms, general terms, genitalia terms, and religious terms were identified in the selected under-study movies, which were found in 1128 cases. The general terms were the most type used in the taboo word category followed by the excretion terms as the second type used in the taboo word category. Besides, based on Davoodi's (2009) model, the findings showed that "Censorship", and "Substitution" were the first and second used strategies by Iranian translators for subtitling the taboo words, respectively. The findings of the Chi-square test revealed significant differences between translators' strategies in four subtitling studios in Iran. These findings offer insights for subtitlers and translation students working on subtitling taboo words from English to Persian in crime movies.

Key words: Audiovisual, Subtitling, Taboo Words, Translation Strategies.

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1. Introduction

Language and culture are intricately intertwined, with language serving as a fundamental tool for communication and cultural expression. This strong relation is evident as language often reflects cultural norms and values. Culture is a complex system that includes social, religious, ritual, educational, kinship, and linguistic aspects, all of which shape individuals' beliefs, values, and behaviors. As a form of socially acquired knowledge, culture plays a crucial role in shaping language. Through language, individuals express a

wide range of emotions and ideas, capturing the essence of human existence. Language enables the expression of diverse emotions, from anger and sadness to happiness and frustration. In addition, the use of politeness and impoliteness in language reflects various emotional contexts, allowing individuals to convey their thoughts through a variety of linguistic styles.

Specifically, nowadays, American movies are popular for entertainment and language learning, yet they often contain taboo words and expressions used by characters to express a range of emotions. Taboo expressions have long been intrinsic to language and culture, serving as essential elements in communication across various societies (Robinson, 1996). Taboos are transmitted through generations, ingrained in subconscious behavior, and persisting through somatic reactions (Robinson, 1996). Ljung (2011) categorizes taboo language into themes like religious, scatological, reproductive organs, sexual activities, and maternal themes. Taboo words wield significant linguistic impact in diverse contexts such as everyday conversations, music, online platforms, and films. Despite being discouraged as impolite expressions, taboo words are increasingly used in contemporary society to convey emotional expression. Taboos, inherent in culture and language, pose significant challenges in translation. Sharifian and Darchinyan (2009) propose a model categorizing taboos in Hollywood audio-visual content, including (a) Private relations between men and women whether legitimate or illegitimate, (b) boys' and girls' relations before marriage; (c) calling or naming outer sexual organs and related words; (d) words and expressions related to alcoholic drinks and drugs; (e) swearing, curse, and impolite expressions; (f) stating features of immoral behaviors and habits like thieving, etc.; (g) issues related to religion and belief which are against those of the translator's society; and (h) stating some political issues which are rather threatening to the translator's society. Translators face the complex task of transferring taboo words between languages, requiring a deep understanding of both source and target languages. Translators face challenges dealing with these taboo words as they must navigate both linguistic and cultural nuances (Nasery & Pishkar, 2015). In Iran, translators encounter numerous difficulties in translating taboo words, employing diverse strategies to convey them in Persian while adapting them for local audiences (Alavi et al., 2013). The complexity intensifies as certain elements of taboo words, deemed inappropriate in Iranian culture, must be omitted, posing a significant challenge to maintaining the movie's coherence (Danaeefar et al., 2020). The translation problem becomes even more complicated when it comes to subtitling since they are subject to some more limitations (Pratama, 2017). There are numerous strategies that translators apply to transfer taboo words from the source text to the target text. Hence, Davoodi (2009) suggests strategies such as censorship, substitution, taboo for taboo, and euphemism to navigate these challenges effectively.

Taboo expressions are considered one of the most problematic issues in Audiovisual Translation (AVT) for almost all translators. AVT, a generic term equivalent to Screen Translation or Media Translation, presents a new frontier in Translation Studies (TS), encompassing subtitling and dubbing as major forms of translation. AVT, a critical aspect of media translation, extends beyond traditional written and oral translation, incorporating voice-over, narration, free commentary, and partial dubbing (Diaz Cintas, 2008; Gambier, 2018). Subtitling, as described by Chiaro (2009), involves overlaying written text onto

screens, catering to various digital platforms like television, mobile devices, and cinema screens. Dubbing, as explained by Chaume (2012), entails replacing original dialogue in a source language with translated dialogue recorded in the target language, preserving soundtrack components like music and special effects.

While European countries show a growing interest in AVT research, Iran lags behind in exploring translation strategies for taboo words in subtitling English Hollywood crime movies into Persian. In this regard, four Hollywood English crime films *Training Day* (2001), *21 Jump Street* (2012), *Alpha Dog* (2007), and *Straight Outta Compton* (2015) were selected as the corpus of the study, and the taboo words in the four mentioned films were identified. The identification of taboo words in these movies based on Hughes' (1998) model sets the foundation for examining the subtitling strategies employed in translating taboos into Persian within the Iranian cultural context, guided by Davoodi's (2009) model. The study aims to statistically compare the translation strategies applied in subtitling taboo words across the selected crime movies, seeking to identify any significant differences based on Davoodi's (2009) model. Considering the purpose of this study, the following research questions were presented:

Q1. What types of taboo words were most frequently utilized in the selected crime movies according to Hughes' (1998) model?

Q2. What were the predominant strategies employed by Iranian translators when subtitling taboos from English to Persian in the selected crime movies, guided by Davoodi's (2009) model?

Q3. Is there any significant difference in the strategies utilized by Iranian translators across four subtitling studios when subtitling the taboos in the selected crime movies?

2. Literature Review

In the contemporary landscape, individuals are immersed in a plethora of audiovisual materials across various settings facilitated by a range of screens such as TVs, cinemas, DVD players, cell phones, and computers (Diaz Cintas, 2008). This prevalence of visual media characterizes the current era as screen-centric (Bogucki, 2004). Initially marginalized within translation studies due to its close ties to cinema and film studies and the absence of a cohesive paradigm (Bogucki, 2004; Remael, 2010), Audiovisual Translation (AVT) has now emerged as a recognized and integral component of Translation Studies (TS) (Diaz Cintas, 2008; Diaz Cintas & Anderman, 2009; Gambier, 2018). The "audiovisual turn" in the 21st century has propelled AVT modes, platforms, devices, and consumption habits (Chaume, 2013). AVT transcends mere screen translation or film translation to encompass the translation of multimedia content, like videos, audio, and images (Pablos-Ortega, 2023), spanning diverse genres such as documentary films, cinema films, televised broadcasts, and home videos (Hmidi, 2023). The term "audiovisual texts" denotes media reception through visual and acoustic channels involving rapidly changing images (Bartrina, 2004). This multidisciplinary field integrates film studies, translatology, semiotics, linguistics, psychology, and technology (McLoughlin et al., 2023). Translating audiovisual content poses distinct challenges like translating non-verbal elements and culture-specific notions

(Estelyi-Tala & Hortobagyi, 2022), necessitating specialized skills including language proficiency, visual acuity, and information condensation abilities (Vulpoi, 2021). Two prevalent techniques employed to enable viewers devoid of linguistic familiarity to engage with audiovisual content are subtitling and dubbing (Estelyi-Tala & Hortobagyi, 2022).

Dubbing

Dubbing, a process involving the translation and synchronization of scripts with audiovisual content, is executed by artists under the guidance of a dubbing director (Chaume, 2020). Language consultants or voiceover assistants play a crucial role in providing expertise and advice (Minutella, 2020). Academic reformulation of the text is considered necessary, reflecting the prevailing attitude towards duplication reflecting the nature of translations for mass consumption, with duplication seen as a tool of colonialism (Chaume, 2013; Paolinelli & Di Fortunato, 2005; Plourde, 2000). Dubbing involves recording new audio tracks by voice actors to replace the original language spoken by the actors during filming. The new sound is synchronized with the actors' lip movements on the screen (Martínez, 2004). The purpose of dubbing is to create a credible illusion of the original product in the target language (Matamala, 2010). During dubbing, foreign lines of dialogue are adapted to match the original film's actors' lip movements and original sentence lengths, known as isochrony (Aljuied, 2021, Kumar et al., 2023).

Subtitling

Subtitling, per Chen (2019) and Diaz Cintas and Remael (2014), displays translated text at the screen bottom, aiming to faithfully render verbal exchanges and visual elements such as text inserts and signs. Chaume (2018) notes subtitles also translate auditory components like songs and background voices. All subtitled programs consist of three essential elements: spoken language, visual content, and subtitles provided (Vanderplank, 2016). Audiovisual media's essence lies in the viewer's ability to comprehend visual images and text at a suitable pace on screen size (Gambier, 2018). Synchronization with dialogue and image is crucial in academic subtitling (Diaz Cintas & Remael, 2014), ensuring semantic accuracy (Gottlieb, 2012). In addition, adequate screen time aids viewers' comprehension (Perego et al., 2010).

Concept and Characteristics of Taboos

Taboos are cultural representations within linguistic societies, with attitudes varying across different societies (Nazari Robati & Zand, 2018). Some of these expressions are culture-specific, so some terms may be forbidden in one language but not in another one due to religious and political attitudes (Alipour & Hadian, 2017). Taboo language is a means of expressing emotions and is present in everyday life and audiovisual products like movies (Rahmayani & Fitrawati, 2018). The term "taboo" originates from the Polynesian language "tapu", meaning "prohibited" or "forbidden" (Gilmore et al., 2013). It was integrated into English in the eighteenth century (Fershtman et al., 2011; François, 2022).

Taboos are deeply rooted in societal customs and transmitted across generations. They serve diverse purposes, from individual protection to ecological or spiritual significance (Meyer-Rochow, 2009). The term was translated as consecrated, inviolable,

forbidden, unclean, or cursed (Biggs, 2012). The concept of taboo encompasses behaviors deemed detrimental to society members, evoking feelings of anxiety or shame (Fromkin et al., 2013; Wardhaugh, 2006). According to Fromkin et al. (2013), the taboo has a strong cultural component representing particular customs and the way people view their society. It is argued that culture-specific items like taboos are intrinsic to societal customs and play a crucial role in shaping society (Yuryevna Ermolenko et al., 2020). These prohibitions persist over time and are characterized by their inappropriate nature in everyday communication. Taboo words typically convey emotions like disgust, social norm violation, sexual connotations, and anger (Robinson, 1996, p.24). Researchers like Ghounane (2014), Allan and Burrige (2006), and Natalie (2005) have explored the diverse facets of taboo language, highlighting its associations with banned behaviors, insults, sexual references, and cultural sensitivities. The present study utilized Hughes's (1998) model to identify and categorize taboo words in the study corpus. Hughes (1998) classifies taboo words into seven distinct types, each elucidated below in alphabetical order:

- **Anatomy terms:** It includes taboo words related to the human body, including terms like tit, a*s, you're a*s, ars**le/as**le, God rot your bones, and damn your eyes!
- **Animal terms:** It is linked to animal terms portraying human beings as stupid, filthy, and unconscious, with examples including snakes, pigs, cows, donkeys, and monkeys.
- **Excretion terms:** These taboos are linked to the excretory system of living beings, featuring words like feces, waste, flatulence, falsehoods, filth, and despicable individuals.
- **General Terms:** This type includes taboos without specific meaning, encompassing terms like an imbecile, fornicator, despicable person, despicable mother figure, illegitimate child, and expressions like damn/darn, punk, coward, and son of a despicable person.
- **Genitalia terms:** This category encompasses taboos that are related to genital functions and sexual terms. These terms primarily refer to the vagina and penis. Examples include derogatory terms like female genitalia, male genitalia, testicles, and scrotum.
- **Religion terms:** This category comprises taboos associated with God, religion, and religious figures, often influenced by Christianity. Examples encompass terms like "by God!" and "You damned villain," "God damn" and "damn Jesus", along with sacred references, such as "on my m*ther's grave".
- **Stupidity terms:** This category features taboo words used to insult intelligence or express frustration, reflecting a lack of intelligence or self-respect. Examples include terms like "Idiot", "dummy," "imbecile," "moron," "fool ya," and "ignoramus," as well as more modern terms like "d**khead," "f**kwit," "gink," "git," "nutter," and slang terms like "fruitcake" for someone considered slightly insane.

Sharifi and Darchinyan (2009) in a local study identified eight categories of taboo language for Persian translators as follows:

- Private relations between men and women including legitimate or illegitimate interactions;
- pre-marriage relationships like boyfriend, girlfriend;
- Naming sexual organs and related words;
- Words about alcoholic drinks and drugs;

- Swearing, cursing, and impolite expressions;
- Describing immoral behaviors like thieving;
- Issues related to religion conflicting with the translator's society;
- Stating some political issues that are rather threatening to the translator's society.

Strategies for Translating Taboo Words

Since taboos are part of the culture of any language, translating a taboo requires the translator to be familiar with the source and target languages to know whether the taboo word in the source language (SL) is known as a taboo in the target language. (TL). Behzad and Salmani (2013) identified three consequences when translating taboo terms: a) a taboo in the source language (L1) may not be taboo in the target language (L2), b) a taboo remains taboo across both languages and c) a term that is not considered taboo. Translators face complexities in parts (b) and (c), requiring nuanced choices to convey similar meanings and emotions. Various strategies exist for translating taboo terms, with translators selecting approaches based on context. Davoodi (2009) outlined four strategies:

Censorship: The translator chooses to easily ignore the term and treat it as a foreign element. However, it must be recognized that this particular choice is inappropriate, as there are cases where the term taboo is important as an essential concept in the original text.

- **Substitution:** Replacing the taboo with an appropriate equivalent, which may alter the intended meaning.
- **Taboo for Taboo:** Transferring the unacceptable taboo words into the taboo language, acknowledging their inappropriateness.
- **Euphemism:** Using more acceptable or non-offensive terms to convey negative connotations or unpleasant ideas or soften negative connotations.
- Khoshsaligheh and Ameri (2014) proposed four strategies for translating taboo words as follows:
 - **Taboo-to-Taboo:** Maintaining the offensiveness levels by translating swear words to equivalents in the target language.
 - **Taboo-to-non-taboo:** Neutralizing the swear words with non-taboo expressions.
 - **Euphemisation/softening:** Using euphemistic expressions to tone down swear words.
 - **Omission:** Deleting swear words in the target language.

Robinson (2006) also presented seven translation strategies for translating taboo words as follows:

- **Borrowing:** Adapting words from another language while maintaining the original word's essence and just changing spoken rules in the target language.
- **Censorship or Omission:** Removing specific elements from the source text during translation.
- **The phenomenon of euphemism:** Substituting offensive terms with more agreeable or non-offensive ones.
- **Substitution:** Replacing taboo terms with other alternatives in the second language (L2).
- **Taboo for taboo:** Preserving both the expressive and propositional meanings by translating taboo expressions equivalently.

- Translation by more general words: Using broader terms in the target text to convey the essence of taboo expressions from the source text.

3. Method

Corpus of the Study

In the present study, four English Hollywood crime movies *Training Days* (2001), *21 Jump Street* (2012), *Alpha Dog* (2007), and *Straight Outta Compton* (2015) were chosen as the corpus of the study. This diverse selection provides a comprehensive dataset for examining crime genres, cultural representations, and subtitling practices in English Hollywood cinema.

The first movie, *Training Day* (2001), directed by Antoine Fuqua and written by David Ayer, is a 122-minute American thriller movie that received critical acclaim, earning Denzel Washington Academy Award for Best Actor in 2001 and numerous other accolades.

21 Jump Street (2012), directed by Phil Lord and Kris Miller, based on a TV series, is a 109-minute action comedy-crime film. The screenplay by Michael Bacall, with a story by Michael Bacall and Jonah Hill, received positive reviews and was the 14th highest-grossing movie in America in 2014. It won 11 awards and received 21 nominations, with a 69% approval rating on Metacritic.

Alpha Dog (2007), a crime drama directed by Nick Cassavetes, depicts the true story of Nicholas Markowitz's kidnapping and murder in 2000. The film, with seven nominations and three awards, explores the complex dynamics of friendship control.

Straight Outta Compton (2015), an American biographical drama/crime film directed by F. Gary Gray, portrays the rise of the N.W.A, revolutionizing hip-hop culture. The film received 45 nominations and three awards and was praised for its entertainment value and cultural significance.

Noteworthy, English and Persian subtitles for *21 Jump Street* and *Training Day* were sourced from the Subf2m and Tiny Movie studio, respectively, as an acceptable subtitled version for further analysis. However, the subtitles for *Straight Outta Compton* (2015) were obtained from Subkade studio to explore the subtitle taboo model. Notably, in Iran, Digimovie was the only studio that subtitled *Alpha Dog* (2006).

Table 1 The Movies selected for the Corpus Study

	Movies			
	Alpha Dog	21 Jump Street	Training Day	Straight Outta Compton
Director	Nick <u>Cassavetes</u>	<u>Phile</u> Lord and Kris Miller	Antoine Fuqua	F. Gary Gray
Genre	Crime Drama	Crime Drama	Crime	Crime Drama
Released date	January 12, 2007	2012	2001	August 14, 2015
Language	English	English	Language	English
Running Time	117 minutes	109 minutes	122 minutes	147 minutes
Awards	3	11	17	15
Subtitle Company	<u>digimovie.plus</u>	Subf2m	Tiny Movie	Subkade.ir

Procedure

To achieve the study objectives, a systematic approach was followed. Initially, four films were purposefully selected as primary data sources for extracting and classifying taboo words. Using Hughes' (1998) model, an exhaustive analysis of all 495 minutes of these movies was conducted to extract taboo words. Subsequently, a comprehensive table was constructed to organize the identified words, with columns for the original text, subtitles, subtitle translation strategies, and film duration. The researchers meticulously watched the original versions to document all instances of taboo words and their timestamps. Afterward, the subtitled versions were reviewed to identify Persian equivalents for the English taboo words. English taboo words were entered in the original text column, while their Persian counterparts were recorded in the subtitling columns. Finally, each instance of taboos underwent detailed analysis using Davoodi's (2009) translation strategies framework to assess the frequency, percentage distribution, and significant differences in translation.

Data Analysis Method

To address the first and second research questions, the data underwent entry into SPSS version 26 for analysis. A descriptive statistical method was employed to examine the frequency and percentage of strategies applied by Iranian translators in subtitling taboo words. For the final aspect of the third research question, a Chi-square statistical analysis was conducted to statistically compare the frequencies obtained. This comparison aimed to identify differences between different translation strategies utilized in subtitling taboo words into Persian.

4. Results

Result of the First Research Question

To address the first research question on categorizing taboo words in crime movies per Hughes' (1998) model, descriptive statistics (i.e., frequency and percentage) were

applied. Table 2 illustrates taboo word categories in selected crime movies. The analysis summarized taboo words in four movies, revealing General Terms as the most common at 91.22% and Religion Terms as the least at 0.53%. Additionally, the Excretion Terms, Genitalia Terms, and Anatomy Terms ranked as the second, third, and fourth most frequent at 3.55%, 2.66%, and 2.04%, respectively. Examples of each translation strategy in the movies are detailed in the subsequent sections.

Table 2 Frequencies and Percentages of Taboo Words in the Four Selected Crime Movies

Types of Taboo Words		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Anatomy Term	23	2.04
	Excretion Terms	40	3.55
	General Terms	1029	91.22
	Genitalia Terms	30	2.66
	Religion Terms	6	0.53
	Total	1128	100.0

General Terms

Based on Hughes' (1998) model these taboo words fall under the category of general terms with curse meaning. General taboos, which are not bound by specific meanings, are commonly used to express anger or frustration. Examples include derogatory terms like imbecile, fornicator, despicable individual, despicable mother figure, and illegitimate child. Analysis revealed that the General Terms, with 1029 instances (91.22%), predominated as the primary type of taboo word in the selected movies. Specific examples are detailed in Table 3 for reference.

Table 3 Samples of General Terms in the Selected Movies

NO.	English Corpus	Movie	Time
1	You shot my partner, you m*therF*ker!	Jump Street 21	01:38:23
2	You m*therF*ker . Hey, jackers .	Training Day	00:46:22
3	I gotta kill this m*therf**ker , Suge Knight .	Straight Outta Compton	01:49:27

Excretion Terms

In alignment with Hughes' (1998) model, these taboo words pertain to the excretory system, mostly in humans and animals, including terms like sh*t, turd, fart, bulls**t, filthy, and scum. Excretion Terms, totaling 40 instances and representing 3.55% of data, emerged as the second category of taboo terms in the analyzed crime movies (Table 4).

Table 4 Samples of Excretion Terms in the Selected Movies

NO.	English Corpus	Movie	Time
1	Yeah, yeah. Just make sure you get the sh*t smell out of the carpet, bi**h! .	Alpha Dog	00:33:49
2	It's 90 percent bulls**t , but it's entertaining.	Training Day	00:05:37
3	I've never done this sh*t before	Jump Street 21	01:29:13

Anatomy Terms

Following Hughes' (1998) model, this category of taboo words is associated with the human body, including terms like tit, a*s, you're a*s, ars***le/as**le, God rots your bones, etc. Anatomy Terms were observed 23 times and accounted for 2.04% of the total, ranked as the third most utilized taboo words in the designated movies (Table 5).

Table 5 Samples of Anatomy Terms in the Selected Movies

NO.	English Corpus	Movie	Time
1	I'm gonna jump your a*s <u>es</u> off Jump Street!	Jump Street 21	01:05:25
2	Let's kick his a*s.	The Alpha Dog	01:11:43
3	If you f**k with me I'll put my foot in you're a*s	The Straight Outta Compton	00:20:17

Genitalia Terms

Based on Hughes' (1998) model, this category pertains to genital functions and sex terms, encompassing derogatory terms like female genitalia, male genitalia, testicles, and scrotum. This category represented the fourth type of taboo term in the analyzed movies, with a frequency of 30 instances and a percentage of 2.66 (Table 6).

Table 6 Samples of Genitalia Terms in the Selected Movies

NO.	English Corpus	Movie	Time
1	You say you want to s**k my c**k, right?	The Alpha Dog	00:04:25
2	Your grandma's v* <u>gina</u> , and there's a d**k going into it.	Jump Street 21	00:33:28
3	You're getting f**ked real quick and <u>Eazy's</u> d**k is smelling like MC <u>Ren's</u> sh*t	The Straight Outta Compton	01:36:10

Religion Terms

Following Hughes' (1998) model, Religion Terms encompass words associated with God, religious beliefs, and practice. Examples include the devil, expressions like "by God!", and phrases like "Goddamn" and "damn Jesus." Religion Terms, with a frequency of 6 instances and representing 0.53% of the total, were the least frequently encountered taboo words in the examined movies (Table 7).

Table 7 Samples of Religion Terms in the Selected Movies

NO.	English Corpus	Movie	Time
1	Whoa, goddamn it, man!	The Alpha Dog	00:19:51
2	Goddamn it, man!	Training Day	00:47:15
3	We can own the goddamn world, ...	The Straight Outta Compton	01:43:05

Result of the Second Research Question

The second research question seeks to explore the strategies employed by Iranian translators when subtitling taboo words from English to Persian in the four chosen crime

movies. Table 8 indicated that the most frequently utilized strategy was "Censorship", accounting for 411 cases, or 36.44% of the total. Following closely was the "Substitution" strategy, with 321 instances making up 28.46% of the total. The "Taboo for Taboo" strategy ranked third in frequency, with 294 occurrences representing 26.06% of the total. Lastly, the "Euphemism" strategy was the least utilized, with only 102 cases, making up 9.04% of the total instances of subtitling taboo words. In general, it is worth noting that the strategies of "Censorship," "Substitution," "Taboo for Taboo," and "Euphemism," have been employed in the subtitling of the selected crime movies following Davoodi's (2009) model.

Table 8 Frequencies and Percentages of Translation Strategy in Selected Crime Movies

Translation Strategies in Subtitled Versions	Frequency	Percent
Censorship	411	36.44
Substitution	321	28.46
Taboo for Taboo	294	26.06
Euphemism	102	9.04
Total	1128	100.0

Censorship

The utilization of the censorship strategy in translation involves selectively omitting or masking specific elements from the ST during the translation process into the TL. Chesterman (2017) notes that when confronted with taboo expressions, translators may opt for a "censorship" strategy, where they eliminate taboo elements from the ST to temper their impact in the TT. This decision could be driven by the translator's intention to align with the linguistic norms of the target audience or by the inadequacy of the original words within the cultural and linguistic context of the TL. The censored content typically comprises words containing taboo language and associated derivatives, often employed to emphasize a point or convey intense emotions, frequently with sexual connotations. This strategy emerged as the primary and most frequently employed approach, with 411 instances, representing 36.44% of the total (Table 8). Table 9 showcases three specific examples of censorship strategies implemented by subtitlers in the examined movies.

Table 9 Examples of Censorship Strategy in Persian Subtitled Version of the Selected Movies

Movies	Source Text	Sub version
Jump Street 21	Go ahead. You won't find s*t.	باشه بگرد، هیچی پیدا نمیکنی.
The Alpha Dog	Dude, you are a f**king full-on	کارت تمومه
The Straight Outta Compton	Keep your m*therf**kin' hands to yourself.	سرت تو کار خودت باشه

Substitution

As per Baker (1992), "substitution" is characterized by the replacement of specific expressions, particularly taboo words, with an element in the TL that may not convey the exact meaning but can elicit a similar response from the target audience. Altered content mainly includes words featuring profanity, derogatory language, and negative remarks such as profanity and pejoratives, which are considered impolite and prohibited. The

"Substitution" strategy emerged as the second most prevalent strategy in subtitling, encompassing 321 instances or 28.46% of the total occurrences (Table 8). Subtitlers opted for this strategy to translate taboo words from English to Persian.

Table 10 Examples of Substitution Strategy in Persian Subtitled Version of the Selected Movies

Movies	Source Text	Sub version
The Alpha Dog	Do you see the f**king moon, Elvis?	ماه ل**تی رو تو آسمون میبینی؟ الویس
The Straight	- Why are you tripping, homes?	چرا قاطی کردین، رفقاً؟
Outta Compton	- Back up, freak- a*s !	گمشو عقب عوضی
Training day	Get the f**k out of my car, rookie.	گ**تو از ماشینم گم کن بیرون تازه کار.

Taboo for Taboo

In this approach, the translator modifies the culturally sensitive language of the ST to align with the cultural nuances of the TL, ensuring the preservation of both expressive and propositional meanings. As described by Vinay and Darbelnet (2000), the TT must uphold its original syntax, meaning, and style. Consequently, the "Taboo for Taboo" strategy emerges as the third most utilized approach by subtitlers, with a frequency of 294 instances, accounting for 26.06% of the total occurrences. Table 11 shows how subtitlers applied the "Taboo for Taboo" strategy to translate taboo words from English into Persian.

Table 11 Examples of Taboo for Taboo Strategy in Persian Subtitled Version of the Movies

Movies	Source Text	Sub version
The Alpha Dog	Shut the f**k up, bi**h . S**k my c**k	خفه شو ک***ش برام س*ک ب*ن
Jump Street 21	D.B., shoot these motherf**kers .	دی بی به این حر**زاده ها شلیک کن.
Training day	Was she a dyke, a le**ian ?	هم**س یاز بود؟

Euphemism

The "euphemism" strategy entails substituting a less offensive expression with one that may carry unpleasant undertones. The main aim is to shield audiences from potential offense by minimizing the use of profane language, offensive expressions, and vulgar descriptions (Al-Shahwi, 2013). The results revealed that subtitlers implemented the "euphemism" strategy in 102 instances, representing 9.04% of the total occurrences. This strategy ranked as the least utilized strategy for translating taboo words (Table 8). Table 12 offers specific examples illustrating how subtitlers integrated the "euphemism" strategy into translations.

Table 12 Examples of Euphemism Strategy in Persian Subtitled Version of the Selected Movies

Movies	Source Text	Sub version
The Straight Outta Compton	My man Dre'll <u>f**k</u> you up in a minute	رفیقم، در عرض یه دقیقه <u>دخلت</u> رو میاره
Jump Street 21	I'm <u>gonna</u> jump <u>your a*ses</u> off Jump Street!	من شما رو از خیابون جامپ اخراج میکنم.
Training day	That was some pretty amazing <u>s**t</u> you did back there, Hoyt.	کار توپی رو میگم که اونجا انجام دادی.

Result of the Third Research Question

The Chi-square test was employed to address the third research question, focusing on the difference in strategies utilized by translators for subtitling taboo words in the chosen crime movies in four subtitling studios in Iran. The analysis revealed a significant difference in three strategies employed, named Censorship, Substitution, and Taboo for Taboo, with a chi-square statistic value of 19.008, 57.331, and 26.457, and a significance value associated with it Sig = 0.005, Sig = 0.001, and Sig = 0.000; respectively, indicating a p-value below .05 (Table 13). This outcome confirms a notable difference in translation strategies for taboo words in the selected movies.

Table 13 Results of the Chi-square Test

			Value	<u>Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)</u>
Censorship	Chi-Square Test	Pearson Chi-Square	18.098	0.005
Taboo for Taboo	Chi-Square Test	Pearson Chi-Square	26.346	0.000
Substitution	Chi-Square Test	Pearson Chi-Square	56.893	0.001
Euphemism	Chi-Square Test	Pearson Chi-Square	4.972	0.183

Table 14 shows that the "Censorship" strategy, with frequencies of 170 and 113 and percentages of 48.16% and 41.9%, emerged as the most prevalent strategy in the Persian subtitled version of Training Day and Straight Outta Compton movie, respectively. In contrast, this strategy ranked second and third in the subtitled versions of the Alpha Dog and Jump Street 21 (Table 15).

More specifically, the "Substitution" strategy, with frequencies of 102 and 66 and percentages of 35.17% and 30.7%, was predominantly utilized in the Persian subtitled versions of Jump Street 21 and Alpha Dog movie. Conversely, it occupied the second and third positions in the subtitled versions of Training Day and Straight Outta Compton crime movies (Table 15).

Table 14 Results of Cross-Tabulation of the Fourth Question in the Selected Crime Movies

Translation Strategies	Jump Street 21		Training day		Alpha Dog		Straight Outta Compton	
	<u>Frg</u>	<u>Perc</u>	<u>Frg</u>	<u>Perc</u>	<u>Frg</u>	<u>Perc</u>	<u>Frg</u>	<u>Perc</u>
Euphemism	27	9.31	9	2.55	35	16.28	31	11.5
Substitution	102	35.17	92	26.06	66	30.7	61	22.6
Censorship	64	22.07	170	48.16	64	29.77	113	41.9
Taboo for Taboo	97	33.45	82	23.23	50	23.25	65	24.1
Total	290	100.0	353	100.0	215	100.0	270	100.0

Moreover, the "Taboo for taboo" strategy, with frequencies of 97 and 65 and percentages of 33.45%, and 24.1%, was the second most employed strategy in the Persian subtitled versions of Jump Street 21 and Straight Outta Compton (Table 14). In contrast, it ranked third in the subtitled versions of Training Day and Alpha Dog movies. Furthermore, the "Euphemism" strategy was observed to be the least used strategy in the Persian subtitled versions of taboo words in all selected crime movies (Table 15).

Table 15 Results of Differences between the Strategies Employed by Four Subtitling Studios

No.	Movies	Subtitling Studio	Translation Strategies Ranks			
			First	Second	Third	Last
1	Alpha Dog	<u>Digimovie</u>	Substitution	Censorship	Taboo for Taboo	Euphemism
2	Jump Street 21	<u>Sub2fm</u>	Substitution	Taboo for Taboo	Censorship	Euphemism
3	Training day	Tiny Movie	Censorship	Substitution	Taboo for Taboo	Euphemism
4	Straight Outta Compton	<u>Subkade</u>	Censorship	Taboo for Taboo	Substitution	Euphemism

5. Discussion

The study reveals that Iranian subtitlers predominantly favored the "Censorship" strategy, accounting for 36.44% of instances, as the primary strategy for translating taboo words. The strategy involves omitting culturally sensitive terms from the SL, a decision that can significantly impact the original text's meaning. However, the deliberate exclusion of taboo terms may lead to shifts in the intended meanings, posing challenges to audience interpretation. Besides, the "Substitution" strategy was employed in 28.46% of cases as the second most common strategy. While this strategy offers a straightforward alternative by replacing taboo words with non-taboo alternatives in Persian, it often introduces distortions and confusion, potentially rendering translations nonsensical to audiences.

Additionally, the Iranian subtitlers employed the "Taboo for Taboo" as the third employed strategy was utilized in 26.06% of instances, indicating a preference among subtitlers for substituting taboo words with equivalent expressions in Persian. While this strategy may provide a simplistic resolution, it can evoke unease among the Iranian audience, highlighting the delicate balance between linguistic accuracy and cultural sensitivity. Conversely, the "Euphemism" as the least used strategy, employed in 9.04% of cases, involved neutral or euphemistic rendering to substitute offensive or suggestive expressions in the TL. The utilization of this strategy is recommended for mitigating the expression of offensive terms while maintaining communication clarity.

The results of the Chi-square test underscore a significant difference in the strategies employed for subtitling taboo words in the selected crime movies. The "Censorship" strategy was the most common approach in subtitling taboo words, followed by the "Substitution" and "Taboo for Taboo" strategies. The minimal of the "Euphemism" strategy across all crime movies suggests varying preferences among translators based on cultural contexts and audience expectations. The differences in the frequency of strategies used in subtitling taboo words in different movies may be due to the context and cultural background of the movies. Additionally, this suggests that the choice of strategies for subtitling taboo words varies among translators and may be influenced by factors such as cultural differences, language-specific norms, and the translator's personal preferences. Translators need to be aware of these strategies and adapt them according to the target audience and cultural context to ensure accurate and appropriate translations of taboo words. This can help in maintaining the original meaning and context of the source material while considering the sensitivities and preferences of the target audience.

The findings of this study are in line with the findings of Abu-Rayyash et al. (2023). They explored the translation strategies of swear words in subtitling 40 movies from English into Arabic. The omission strategy was with 66%, the swear-to-non-swear strategy was the least adopted one, 21%. In addition, the softening strategy got the second-highest frequency across the different movie genres, with 39%. Besides, the findings of this study are in line with the findings of Samir (2023) and Samir and Ghiyasi Hashemizadeh (2023). They examined the strategies employed by Iranian translators for handling the translation of taboo words in the American TV series *Big Little Lies* seasons one and two. They found that "Substitution" and "Censorship" were the predominant strategies used, with no significant difference found between subtitling and dubbing approaches. Izdihar et al. (2022) also investigated translation strategies of taboo words in the subtitle of the film *Yowis Ben 2* based on Wijana and Rahmadi's (2016) model from English to Indonesian. The findings unveiled that the prevailing strategy was deletion. Conversely, the strategy demonstrating the lowest frequency of utilization was establishment equivalence. In the same vein, Samir (2024) investigated the translation strategies employed by Iranian male and female translators for taboo words in Mark Manson's *The Subtle Art of Not Giving a F**k*, finding that significant differences exist with males favoring "Substitution" and the "Taboo for Taboo" strategy, and females preferring "Censorship", highlighting how gender influences translation choices and emphasizing the importance of cultural sensitivity in translation.

Furthermore, the findings of the present study are not in line with the findings of Rafika and Sujana (2022). The scholars investigated subtitling strategies taboos in the *Sex*

Education TV Series Season Two based on Gottlieb's (1992) model. They identified that the transfer strategy exhibited the highest frequency of application in translating taboo words, whereas the expansion strategy displayed the lowest frequency of utilization. In addition, the findings of the present study are not in line with the findings of Wu and Wan (2021). They analyzed the translation strategies of taboo words in the subtitling of the TV series *Big Little Lies* Season 1 from English to Chinese based on William's (1975) and Warren's (1992) models. The results showed that the most frequently used translation strategy was literal translation, accounting for 88.6%, while the euphemistic strategies only accounted for 11.4% in total.

Moreover, the findings of the present study are not in line with the findings of Ben Slamia (2020). He focused on the interlingual subtitling of taboo words in 23 American and British films for Arabic audiences. The finding showed that the Transfer strategy was the first and most used frequent strategy, the dislocation was the second strategy, the resignation was the third strategy, and the deletion strategy was the least used frequent strategy. Additionally, Al-Yasin and Rabab'ah (2019) investigated the connotative equivalence of taboo words in the Arabic subtitles of three American movies. The findings revealed euphemism was the first and most used frequent strategy and omission the least used frequent strategy.

Finally, the findings of the present study are not in line with the findings of Pratama (2017). He explored translation strategies for taboo words in the subtitling of *The Help* movie. The results showed that the transfer strategy was the first and most used frequently strategy with a frequency of (27), euphemism as the second (25), and omission (17) as the least used strategy.

6. Conclusion

The translator's attitude toward taboo words depends on the prevailing cultural and ethical norms. This may include rewording the text, softening the language, or retaining the original wording. Words that can be transformed to conform to moral standards are classified as taboo. According to the results of the study, Iranian translators in subtitling used the four strategies described in Davoodi's (2009) model to deal with taboo language, and the dominant strategy was the strategy of "censorship" in subtitling *Training Day* (2001), *21 Jump Street*, *Alpha Dog* (2007), and *Straight Outta Compton* (2015) movies. This is because the Iranian translators wanted to omit, remove, or censor source taboos that cannot be translated into the target language, or that omitting them harms the SL message in subtitling. Taboo words, both spoken and written, are considered unacceptable and forbidden in the Persian language and cultural norms, causing a negative public reaction. This is why translators censored taboo words. Censorship may stem from the belief that presenting certain scenes and content to a Persian audience may lead to imitation of such behavior. However, there are times when such an approach may not accurately convey the author's intended message or the characters' personalities, as removing or changing taboo language in a film fundamentally changes its original connotation. Furthermore, following the implementation of the "Censorship" strategy, the "Substitution" strategy emerged as the second and predominant method utilized in Persian

subtitled renditions of taboo language in the selected crime films. This indicates that Iranian translators chose to replace taboo words with alternative terms that were deemed as non-taboo within the Persian language. As a result, the translators chose to edit out the use of taboo language. However, this approach frequently results in misinterpretation and perplexity among the intended audience in Iran.

The "Euphemism" strategy was the least frequently used strategy in subtitled versions of taboo words. The findings indicate that subtitled translators were aware of the cultural sensitivity towards taboo language among Iranian audiences, and consequently opted to substitute such language with more culturally appropriate and acceptable equivalents in the target language. Therefore, the Iranian audience comprehends the text's literal meaning and experiences a subjective and emotional interpretation of the words. The "Euphemism" strategy renders taboo expressions from the source language (SL) into euphemistic language, thereby mitigating the offensive nature of the original terms and rendering them more socially acceptable and polite. The strategy was utilized to safeguard the Iranian audience from potential sources of offense.

Finally, Iranian subtitlers used the "Taboo for Taboo" strategy as the third common strategy. Iranian subtitlers knew that Iranian audiences did not find taboo language acceptable, however, they substituted taboo words with equivalent expressions in the TL. This strategy is valuable when dealing with culturally sensitive or offensive terms that may not have direct equivalents in the TL. By replacing taboo words with culturally appropriate alternatives, translators aim to maintain the communicative effectiveness of the translation while respecting the cultural norms and sensitivities of the target audience. This strategy enables translators to navigate the challenges posed by taboo words, ensuring that the translated content remains faithful to the original while being culturally appropriate and respectful.

The findings of this study offer a pedagogical implication for translation students, aiding in the recognition of categorizations of various taboo words in audiovisual products. Moreover, the study provides valuable insights for students to identify and understand strategies applied in English to Persian translations of taboo words in the subtitling in audiovisual subtitling. The examples presented in this study serve as practical tools for teaching and learning these strategies effectively. Furthermore, the results are anticipated to benefit translation instructors by enhancing their awareness of the prevalent strategies applied in the translating of taboo words. This knowledge can be integrated into teaching curricula to better equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge in their translation classes. Additionally, the study outcomes can serve as a comprehensive guideline for aspiring translators, including amateur subtitlers and fansubbers within the audiovisual industry.

Further research could include exploring specific cultural norms influencing taboo word translation, comparing translation strategies across diverse cultural backgrounds, analyzing taboo word frequency in movies across languages, investigating ethical considerations in audiovisual translation strategies of taboo words, assessing the effectiveness of different translation strategies, and examining factors influencing translator strategy choice.

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